

EXPERIMENTAL ASSESSMENT AND DATA ANALYSIS OF COLORED PHOTOVOLTAIC IN THE FIELD OF BIPV TECHNOLOGY APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT: Temperature of PV modules always has been a key parameter in order to understand and predict the efficiency of PV technologies. In this work, the analysis of the temperature trend of a selected set of colored BIPV modules is performed, with the aim of correlating the irradiance recorded through a pyranometer to the temperature of the modules, recorded through Pt100 temperature sensors. A description of the different aspects of BIPV concept is provided, and a simulation strategy is introduced to understand the power loss due to the presence of colored layer on the modules' front glass. Furthermore, test facilities available at Eurac Research laboratories and the equipment used during the test campaign are described. As metric of measures, the Ross coefficient k is used to correlate the different PV systems to the temperature rise. The values found after a data calibration and filtering procedure are elaborated and compared with the outcomes of a standard not-colored BIPV installation, located in Bolzano. The modules' temperature measured through Pt100 sensors have been then compared with the results of a thermographic analysis.

Keywords: BIPV integration, data analysis, laboratory tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

The interest of understanding the effects of color on PV modules performance brought us to perform test campaigns on a set of BIPV colored installation present at the Outdoor Eurac Research PV Integration Lab, and on a standard not-colored BIPV installation at Ex-Post Building in Bolzano [1]. Both installations are located in Bolzano, Italy. The present study focuses on BIPV system energy performance in operating temperature conditions. The set of analyzed colored BIPV modules consists of roof integrated BIPV systems with different customization techniques, that mimic the appearance of standard construction materials and hide the PV cells to the view: one, hereby called "Terracotta", presents a uniform color of the front glass, similar to the classical tiles color (indicative RAL 8015); the other, hereby called "Tegola-Tiles" reproduces a typical tiles pattern, which is digitally printed on the module's front glass [2]

2 INTEGRATION OF COLORED BIPV MODULES IN BUILDINGS

The balance of technical aspect and aesthetical requirements is a key aspect of BIPV systems; from literature and standard definitions of BIPV, three integration areas are defined: aesthetical, technological, and energetic [2]. Therefore, a key aspect to consider for BIPV installations is the appearance that PV modules have on the aesthetic perception of the building elements and of the building as a whole. The purpose of integrating colored PV in buildings is to obtain feasible solutions which can be flexible, visually pleasing, colorful, and that can satisfy the requests of designers in order to create original visual effects and make the building less energy demanding.

3 COLORED BIPV MODULES PERFORMANCE: SIMULATION STRATEGY

3.1 Colored glass characteristics

Recent analysis on colored glass tried to find an effective manner to measure and quantify the efficiency due to the different technology and color which is adopted for BIPV. The work [3] gives guidelines on color efficiency and power loss based on the RAL color classification. For the purpose of this study, the spectral optical characteristics of the colored glasses have been obtained via spectrophotometry and used for calculating the energy transmitted through the front glass.

3.2 Analytical model

An analytical simulation of the "Terracotta" modules was performed, with the purpose of developing an effective methodology to calculate the performance of colored PV. The simulation strategy takes as inputs some results of the indoor tests performed over the selected set of PV modules, consisting of flash tests with a STC irradiation source, compliant with the standard IEC 60904. The aim is to obtain the modules electrical characteristics starting from standard conditions and basic information to get at first the modules I_{sc} . By using then the single diode equation [4], shunt resistance, the glass transmittance data, solar simulator irradiation spectrum, and PV cell characteristics, was possible to get the mayor features of a PV module as IV curve, I_{MPP} , V_{MPP} , P_{MPP} , FF and efficiency. At this point the efficiency was calculated, by using the formula $\eta = P_M / (I_{rrSTC} A_{mod}) \cdot 100$. in order to compare the obtained values with the literature outcomes. Different efficiency were found depending on the considered configurations. The values differ only for a 0.5% over the efficiency outcomes (Table I), with the implementation of the analytical model of Figure 1.

Figure 1: Developing of the analytical model. Eurac Research

Table I: Comparison of the efficiency values found. Eurac Research.

	efficiency (%)
Analytical simulated	12.67
Flash test	13.07

4 EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN

4.1 Ross coefficient: colored modules at Eurac Research PV Integration Lab

By calculating the Ross coefficient [5] it is possible to correlate the temperature of the cell (and module), to the air temperature and the irradiance illuminating the module, reported by the formula $T_{mod} = T_{amb} + kG$, where k is the Ross coefficient with units of $^{\circ}Cm^2 W^{-1}$ or Km^2W^{-1} , G is the solar irradiance illuminating the module in Wm^{-2} , T_{mod} is the module temperature and T_{amb} is the ambient temperature in $^{\circ}C$. The lower is the Ross coefficient, the lower is the difference between the cell temperature and the ambient temperature. Some reference values are given in Table II.

4.2 Outdoor roof mock-up

The Terracotta and Tegola-Tiles modules selected after an indoor test campaign, were installed on a testbed in the PV Integration Lab of Eurac Research (Figure 2 and Figure 3) [2]; which consists of an outdoor roof mock-up which permits to evaluate and test PV and BIPV modules in real-time conditions. From the operative point of view, it is a rotating structure of 20 square meter plane, with the possibility of tilting up to 60° from the horizontal plane and set the azimuth to any degree value, in order to reproduce any installation conditions [2].

4.3 Design of the experiment

The modules installed were previously tested at the indoor Solare PV Lab, through electroluminescence test and flash test, assuring their correct functioning. The modules were connected in series, creating two separate circuits for the Terracotta modules and the Tegola-Tiles modules. During the installation, 8 Pt100 sensors were attached to the back of the modules (Figure 4). The exact position of the sensors is shown in Figure 5.

A wooden substructure was used to install the modules trough a set of three clamps for each module. The slats position has been taken in account to understand their influence on the temperature detected by the Pt100 sensor. The electrical circuits are connected to a DC/AC inverter, with the purpose of identifying and transmitting the output performance data. The irradiance value is detected through a pyranometer installed at the side of the testbed, on the same modules' plan.

Table II: Values of Ross coefficient for various mounting type. [6]

PV Array mounting type	k ($^{\circ}C /W/m^2$)
Free standing	0.021
Flat roof	0.026
Sloped roof: Well cooled	0.020
Sloped roof: not so well cooled	0.034
Sloped roof: highly integrated, poorly ventilated	0.056
Façade integrated: transparent PV's	0.046
Façade integrated: opaque PV's – narrow gap	0.054

Figure 2: Roof mock-up present at the outdoor PV integration Lab. Eurac Research

Figure 3: Frontal and lateral perspective of the roof mock-up. Eurac Research

Figure 4: Pt100 implementation on the modules back. Eurac Research

Figure 5: Localization of the Pt100 sensor on the test-bed facility. Eurac research

The instrument is a Kipp&Zonen Pyranometer with a spectral range from 285 to 2800 nm, sensitivity 7 to 14 $\mu\text{V}/\text{W}/\text{m}^2$. More specifications are present in [7]. A meteorological station is present near the rood mock-up, measuring the wind velocity, wind direction, air temperature, relative air humidity, diffuse horizontal irradiance, global horizontal irradiance, direct normal irradiance, and sun azimuth.

4.4 Modules description

The used BIPV modules are glass-glass modules, provided with monocrystalline cells, devoid of frame, where a process of mineral coating was utilized to fix the colored layer on the inner surface of the cover glass [8]. The BIPV installation at the Ex-Post consists of a not back ventilated polycrystalline system, integrated on the existing façade of the Ex-Post Building as an external cladding through a metallic structure. The modules under investigation are reported in Figure 6.

5 OUTDOOR TESTING RESULTS

5.1 Temperature calibration

Before implementing the temperature data on elaboration, calibration coefficients were applied to proper obtain values temperature with a linear regression through the formula $T_{\text{cal}} = a \cdot T_{\text{old}} + b$, where T_{cal} is the calibrated temperature, T_{old} the value to correct and a and b the calibration coefficients. In Table III, the calibration coefficient for the eight Pt100 temperature sensors are reported.

5.2 Ross coefficients calculations

The Ross coefficient can be obtained graphically by plotting the irradiance over the temperature difference between the module and the air, achieving an intercept among the scattered plots. The slope of that line represents the value of the Ross coefficient (Figure 7). Some filtering procedures are introduced as also reported in [1]. The filter excludes the points corresponding to a ratio of diffuse and global irradiance higher than 0.20 in order to consider only clear sky conditions, as the direct irradiance component is predominant on the diffuse one.

Figure 6: Polycrystalline (a), Terracotta (b) and Tegola-Tiles (c) modules. Eurac Research.

The Ross coefficient values are calculated for the modules installed at the outdoor PV Integration Lab relatively to the time period (26-02-2021 – 23-04-2021), the outcomes are shown on Figure 7.

The outcomes of Table IV are in line with the literature for a sloped roof (Table II), not so well cooled, as it is the test bed facility of the PV Integration Lab. It is possible to observe that the modules, manufactured with the same technology, but in the higher position on the testbed, register the higher value of Ross coefficient. That is due to the fact that the air behind the module gets warmer in the down-top direction of the test bed. The effect is that the modules which are positioned in the higher locations can benefit less of air cooling and can encounter a higher warming with the same irradiation conditions.

5.3 Performance Ratio (PR) filtering outcomes

A specific filter was applied only on a secondary phase, to observe if relevant changes on the graphs and Ross coefficient values are detected after the filtering implementation (Figure 8). The filter considers only the values which withstand the values of $\text{PR}_{\text{avg}} \pm \sigma$ where PR_{ave} is the average value of performance ratio of the PV array for the considered period, defined by the international standard IEC 61724 [9] $\text{PR} = (E \cdot G_{\text{STC}}) / (P_n \cdot G)$ where E is the instant power produced (W), P_n the array nominal power (W), G_{STC} the irradiance under STC conditions ($1000 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$), G the instant irradiance (W/m^2) σ is the standard deviation. The PR_{avg} for the two considered months is 0.785. (26-02 2021 - 23-04-2021). Comparing these results with those without filters on PR, it is possible to notice that a significant lower amount of points are considered and that the resulting Ross coefficient slightly increases, 3.4% for the 1.3 Tegola-Tile module (from 0.0323 to 0.0334 $^\circ\text{C W}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$); 3.4% for the 2.3 Tegola-Tile module (from 0.0337 to 0.0349 $^\circ\text{C W}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$); 6% for the 3.3 Terracotta module (from 0.0332 to 0.0353 $^\circ\text{C W}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$) and of 1.2% for 5.3 Terracotta module (from 0.0340 to 0.0343 $^\circ\text{C W}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$).

5.4 Wind dependance

An important application of the PR filter is the wind dependance of Ross coefficient. A correlation between the Ross coefficient and wind velocity is thus evaluated plotting $k = (T_{\text{mod,avg}} - T_{\text{amb}}) / G$ against wind velocity expressed in m/s (Figure 9). The filtering procedure had effect on leaving out the mayor outliers, producing a graph with a higher degree of accuracy. It is possible to notice that the trend is linear descending, toward the maximum value of wind velocity of about 5 m/s. The wind in this case has only a slight effect due to the fact that the modules are installed over a metallic structure of the test bed and the wooden slats do not allow a greater natural ventilation under the BIPV modules.

Table III: Calibration coefficients values for the 8 Pt100 temperature sensor.

Temperature sensor	a	b
Pt100 T1	1.0056	-0.0885
Pt100 T2	1.0086	-0.1523
Pt100 T3	1.0092	-0.0882
Pt100 T4	1.0319	-0.2822
Pt100 T5	1.0089	0.0712
Pt100 T6	1.0206	-0.1319
Pt100 T7	1.0101	-0.076
Pt100 T8	1.0274	-0.137

Figure 7: $T_{mod}-T_{amb}$ vs G for the 1.3(a), 2.3(b) Tegola-Tile modules and 3.3(c) and 5.3(d) Terracotta modules. Eurac Research

Figure 8: $T_{mod}-T_{amb}$ vs G for the 1.3(a), 2.3(b) Tegola-Tile and 3.3(c), 5.3(d) Terracotta modules after PR filtering. Eurac Research

Table IV: Values of Ross coefficient of the installed modules. Eurac research.

Module	k ($^{\circ}C/W/m^2$)
Tegola 1.3	0.0323
Tegola 2.3	0.0337
Terracotta 3.3	0.0331
Terracotta 5.3	0.0339

Figure 9: Wind dependance of the Ross coefficient. Eurac Research

5.5 Thermography measurements

The thermography technique was used to visualize the temperature distribution of the modules installed on the roof mock-up, and then to correlate the temperature registered from Pt100 sensor placed on the backside module and the surface temperature registered with the infrared camera (Figure 10). The thermography measurements were performed in a sunny and cloudless day when the irradiance measured was higher than 800 W/m² to observe proper working thermal behavior. The IR pictures show the longitudinal temperature trend among the modules, with higher temperatures trend among the modules, with higher temperatures on the upper part, descending among the line (Figure 11). The peak temperatures can bring to an erroneous evaluation of the temperature trend, but those sharp increments are due to the metal structure which can be seen through the modules overcoming. The Pt100 sensor is positioned in the upper and lower modules, following the scheme of Figure 12. The variation between the recorded temperature through the Pt100 and the temperature recorded through the thermal camera is small (Table V). The major discrepancy on the sensor Pt100 7 could be given by the border effect which can influence the module surface temperature.

Figure 10: (a) Infrared picture of the outdoor BIPV Terracotta modules. (b) Temperature path detected with the thermo camera software. Eurac Research

Figure 11: Temperature trend over the modules test bed (line 1 of Figure 11). Eurac Research

Figure 12: localization of the Pt100 sensors on the module's backside. Eurac Research

Table V: Temperature recorded with the Pt100 sensor and the thermo camera at the same instant time.

Sensor	T _{measured} (°C)	T _{thermo} (°C)	ΔT(°C)	%
Pt100 T5	44.9	45.1	0.2	0.01
Pt100 T6	46.07	47.29	1.22	2.57
Pt100 T7	44.67	48.34	3.67	7.59
Pt100 T8	47.91	49.31	1.4	2.83

5.6 Ross coefficient: standard modules at Ex-Post building.

To have a meter of comparison, a previous BIPV installation has been considered, in particular the plant present at the Ex-Post building, in the Bolzano railway proximity (Figure 13) [10]. The purpose is to compare the Ross coefficient value of a standard installation against the colored BIPV one.

The data analyzed for the Ross coefficient calculations go from February 2017 to September 2017. A brief filter procedure was made over the irradiance data, excluding negative values for the irradiance.

The following graph displays the module temperature difference above ambient temperature with the increasing irradiance value (Figure 14). The fitting curve was forced to pass to zero, the slope of the blue curve is representing the Ross coefficient k. The value found is 0.0398 °C W⁻¹ m² in accordance with the data presented on [12]. In this case the system is poorly ventilated with a 10 cm air gap on the back modules and the k value found confirmation on table I from literature. In a second step, the PR filtering procedure was applied as in section 5.4, leading to a Ross coefficient value of 0.0408 C W⁻¹ m².

Figure 13: BIPV system of the Ex-post Building. Eurac Research

Figure 14: $T_{\text{mod}}-T_{\text{amb}}$ vs G for the Ex-Post BIPV (a), with the implementation of the PR filter (b). Eurac Research

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this work the analysis of the Ross coefficient of a selected set of colored BIPV modules is performed, with the aim of correlating the irradiance recorded through a pyranometer to the temperature of the module. At first the analyzed BIPV technologies, the test facilities and the design of the experiment have been described. Then the Ross coefficient was introduced as metric of measurement to correlate the temperature rise of the modules to the irradiation level. The outcomes resulting from the data analysis show that values around $0.033 \text{ C W}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$ are consistent with the literature [6]. The results of the analysis from the outdoor PV Integration Lab were compared with the data and the results coming from the standard not-colored BIPV installation present at Bolzano Ex-Post, with a Ross coefficient value of $0.0398 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C W}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$. This higher value is caused by the poorer ventilation conditions of the Ex-Post installation, anyway it is so possible to assert that BIPV installation color customized, with the purpose to encounter aesthetical requirements, *are not affected* by a higher heating up of the modules, which usually brings to a decline of the PV performance.

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